

CHARACTERIZATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF SOME FOREST GROWING SOILS OF ANANDWAN VILLAGE DIST.

CHANDRAPUR, MAHARASHTRA.

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Abstract:

Natural as well as anthropogenic forest succession often affects soil physical, chemical and biological properties. Soil profile as well as surface samples were collected from Miyawaki (Atal Anandwan Ghanwan) and 1m X 1m forest plantation method of Anandwan village District Chandrapur (MS). Collected soil samples were analyzed for different morphological, physical, chemical and selected biological properties (bacterial and fungal count). The texture and colour (hue) of soils varied from sandy clay to clay and 10YR respectively associated with predominantly angular to sub-angular blocky structure and accumulations of few Fe, Mn concretions. Coarse fragments and sand fractions were more in surface as compared to subsurface. The soils were slightly alkaline (pH 7.6) to slightly acidic (pH 6.6), rich in organic carbon associated with medium to high cation exchange capacity along with high amount of bacterial and fungal count. All major and micro nutrients levels were in higher category. Based upon the characteristics, these forest soils were classified as typic haplustepts.

Key words: Soil survey, morphology, exchange capacity.

Introduction

Soils are considered as the integral part of the landscape and their characteristics are largely governed by landform on which they are developed (Sawhney et al. 1992; Sharma et al. 1999). Systematic study of morphology and taxonomy of soils provides information on nature and type of soils, their constraints, potentials, capabilities and their suitability for various uses (Sehgal, 1996). Sustainable management of land resources is essential for food security, maintenance of environment and betterment of the peoples. The forest productivity by and large depends on the quality of soils in which it sustains. For the proper land resources management in forest areas, investigations on the land properties and their constraints is a pre-requisite. A documentation of soil properties in systematic form is one of the vital components in formulating effective land use planning programme (Deshmukh and Bapat 1993). Through the present investigation, the soil resources in a forested region of Anandwan tahsil Warora, dist. Chandrapur (MS) evaluated for their characterization and classification.

Materials and Methods

The study was undertaken in Anandwan, Tahsil Warora, district Chandrapur (MS) and it lies between 20° 14', 53." N and 79° 01' 19.0" E to 20° 16', 23.5" N and 79° 05' 39.0" E. The mean elevation of area varies from 220 to 280 m above mean sea level (MSL) associated with gently sloping (3-8 %), very gently sloping (1-3 %), and nearly level (0 – 1 %) sloping lands. The climate of the area is subtropical; dry sub-humid with ustic soil moisture regime and hyperthermic soil temperature regime. The average rainfall is 1200 mm which is received mostly from southern monsoon. The natural vegetation comprises dry deciduous mixed trees, and grasses. The trees are teak (*Tectona grandis*), khair (*Acacia catechu*), neem (*Azadirachta indica*), tendu (*Diospyros melanoxylon*), behra (*Terminali abalerica*), babul (*Acacia arabica*), shivan (*Gmelina arborea*), palas (*Butea monosperma*), etc. and the grasses are dub (*Impara cuplinatrica*), kural (*Heteropogan contortus*), kundu (*Schema pilosum*) etc. A large percentage of cultivated land is mainly under kharif crops such as paddy (*Oryza sativa*), pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*), cotton (*Gossypium spp.*), soybean (*Glycine max*) and maize (*Zea mays*) while the main rabi crops are wheat (*Triticum spp.*), linseed (*Linum usitatissimum*), chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*), vegetables and about 32 acre orchards are also grown under drip irrigation. The study area falls in the Survey of India Toposheet No.55P/3. Geologically the area mainly occupied by the Deccan basalts followed by sandstone/limestone of Lameta group of cretaceous period.

Profile study were conducted, pedons were selected at Anandwan for their detailed study. The soil samples were collected horizon-wise, air-dried, ground and sieved using 2 mm sieve. The particles larger than 2

mm were washed with water, dried and weighed as coarse fragments. Particle-size analysis of the sample was carried out by international pipette method. Soil clods were collected from the soil horizons for bulk density determination. Morphological characteristics of each of the horizons like depth, colour, texture, volume of gravel, structure, consistence, calcareousness, roots, pores, etc. were recorded. Additional information about pressure faces/slickensides, depth and width of cracks, coarse fragment content in soil expressed on volume basis (%) etc. was also noted.

The analysis of physical, chemical and nutrient properties of collected soil samples were carried out using standard procedures (Black 1965; Jackson 1967; Lindsay and Norvell 1978). The soils were classified as per Soil Taxonomy. (Soil Survey Staff 2003)

Results and Discussion*Morphological characteristics of soil*

Soil morphology refers to the inherent characteristics of the soils acquired during their evolution and retaining impress of one or several genetic factors (AIS & LUS, 1971). This comprises the evaluation and description of soil depth, colour, texture, structure, consistency, and presence of pans, concretions and such other features of horizons of soil profiles as can be perceived in the field. Soil development in the study area is not far different than the general pattern of soil evolution on basaltic landscape under the semi-arid climatic conditions. Major morphologic variations in these soils, however, are attributed to topographic differences- directly through the controlling influence of topography on gravity flow, runoff, infiltration and temperature flux, as well as indirectly through its bearing on microclimate and biotic factors. The detail soil morphological properties of the study area have been presented in Table 1

The soil depth was studied as a total depth of soil solum (A+B horizon) at various physiographic positions. The soil depth is related to slope and degree of erosion (Srivastava et al., 1991). All the pedons were medium to deep.

The colour of the soil is one of the most important morphological characteristics used for soil identification and appraisal. The relief, drainage conditions, presence of organic matter, weathering intensity and time seems to have direct as well as indirect influence on the soil colour. The colour (hue) of soils are 10YR. The dark colour of these soils may be attributed to humus and minerals like titaniferous magnetite (Zonn, 1986). The colour of deep black soils in a basaltic landform of Maharashtra are reported to be very dark grayish brown (Paranjape et al., 1997).

The texture is an expression to indicate the coarseness or fineness of the soil and determined by the relative proportions of the various sized

primary particles in the soil mass. It is one of the fundamental and permanent characteristics that have direct bearing on structure, porosity and consistence. Texture is capable of being judged to a close approximation by feel in the field, and quantitatively estimating through mechanical analysis of soils in the laboratory. Basalt being the parent material of the study area is known to produce higher amount of clay (Eswaran et al., 1988; Murthy et al., 1994). The texture of the study area is sandy clay.

Soil structure refers to the arrangement of primary soil particles into secondary particles, units or peds. The secondary units are characterized and classified on the basis of size, shape and degree of distinctness into classes, types and grades, respectively. This is recognized as one of the most important properties of the soil mass in that it influences the soil in almost all of its reactions, but especially with regard to aeration, moisture, temperature, permeability and water holding capacity. The surface soils of all pedons have crumbly to angular blocky structure (Table 1). Grades and size of structure are found to be related with physiographic position, slope, soil texture *etc.* In general, structure of subsurface soils observed to be increased in terms of size, types and grades which might be due to overburden created by upper soil material. The soil horizons forming pressure faces and slickensides are having coarse, strong, angular blocky structures accumulations of few Fe, Mn concretions. This may be attributed to high shrink and swell phenomena of smectitic clay present in these soils (Prasad *et al.*, 1989).

The dry consistency varied from loose to slightly hard, moist consistency from loose to friable and wet consistency from slightly sticky to slightly plastic. Few, fine and very fine sized roots are observed in the surface layers. The number of roots decreased with depth. Below 100 cm depth there are only very few to few, fine and medium roots

Chemical properties of soils

The pH indicates the potential of ionizable hydrogen ions and represents the degree of acidity and alkalinity in soils. Soil reaction (pH) is a very important physico-chemical soil property which reflects the availability of different plant nutrients and regulates many physico-chemical phenomena in soils. The pH of soils is mostly related to the nature of parent material, climate and topographic situation which determine soil composition. Soil acidity (indicated by a pH <6.5) is due to leaching of exchangeable bases (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+) and concentration of H^+ on the exchangeable complex. Soil alkalinity (indicated by pH >8.5) is due to accumulation of exchangeable sodium on the exchange complex which cause dispersion in soils. The soils were slightly alkaline (pH 7.6) to slightly acidic (pH 6.6).

The electrical conductivity is a measure of soluble salt concentration in the soils. Higher amount of salts in the soils restrict the nutrient uptake and thus affects the plant growth. All the soils were non-saline with EC values ranging from 0.11 to 0.30 dS m^{-1} .

Organic carbon is an indication of organic fractions in soils formed from the microbial decomposition of residues. It acts as major factor regulating organic forms of nitrogen, phosphorus, sulphur and trace elements in the soils (Stevenson, 1982). It also improves the soil structure, infiltration rate and nutrient retention and reduces soil erosion (Smith and Elliott, 1990). Organic carbon ranges from 0.7 to 3.4 g/kg. In general, the organic carbon content decreased gradually with increase in depth, which is mainly due to the accumulation of plant residues on the soil surface and less movement down the profile due to rapid rate of mineralization at higher temperature and adequate soil moisture level. Similar results were observed by Sarkar et al. (2001), Nayak et al. (2001) and Rao et al., (2008). The soils are non calcareous in nature. In general all these soils are highly base saturated soils.

Available macro and micro-nutrient status of soils

Horizon wise available macro and micro nutrients status of soils are discussed here and presented in Table 2 Nitrogen is the most vital major nutrient required by plants for proper growth and development. Soils of the study area are very low to medium in available nitrogen and the nitrogen content in soils ranged from 43 to 188 kg ha^{-1} (Table 2). The data indicate that the available nitrogen content was higher in surface soils as compared to subsoil layers. This might be due to the higher content of organic carbon and most of the microbial activities are dominant in the surface soils. The results were in close agreement reported by Todmal et al. (2008). The variation in available nitrogen content in soils could be attributed to the differences in their physiography as well as the differential cultivation and management of these soils (Patil and Sonar, 1994).

Phosphorus is the second most important major nutrient required by plants after nitrogen for proper growth and development. Soils of Anandwan forest are very low to medium in available phosphorus and the phosphorus content varied 5 to 12 kg ha^{-1} . It is observed from the data in Table 2 that the available phosphorus content decreased with depth in all soils. Low available phosphorus content of these soils could be attributed to their high P-fixing capacity which prevents phosphorus to come into readily available form in the soil solution.

Potassium is the third important major nutrient required by plants for their proper growth and development after nitrogen and phosphorus. Available potassium content in the soils varied from 340.22 kg ha^{-1} to 453.20 kg ha^{-1} (Table 2). The potassium content also increased with the clay content. This may be attributed to the K-rich minerals occurring in the soil (Pal, 1985) and the relative immobility of this element on account of fixation by clay. Most of the surface soils had higher available potassium content which might be due to more intense weathering of potash bearing minerals, generation of leaf litter from different crops in cropping systems, release of labile K from organic residues, application of K fertilizers and upward translocation of K from lower depth with capillary rise of ground water (Hirekurbar et al., 2000 and Patil et al., 2008).

The DTPA-Cu varied from 0.44 to 0.76 mg kg^{-1} . These soils had higher copper content than the critical value of 0.2 mg kg^{-1} (Katyal and Randhawa, 1983). Patil and Kharche (2006) also reported sufficient available copper in the swell-shrink soils of Western Maharashtra. The DTPA-extractable Fe ranged from 2.24 to 2.74 mg kg^{-1} . As per the critical value of DTPA- Fe of 4.5 mg kg^{-1} (Lindsay and Norvell, 1978), the soils were found deficient in available iron (Table 2). The DTPA-Zn ranged from 1.8 to 2.5 mg kg^{-1} . As per the critical level of 0.6 mg kg^{-1} as suggested by Katyal and Randhawa (1983), the soils were found sufficient in zinc. The available Mn ranged from 2.34 to 8.78 mg kg^{-1} . Most of soils under study were found to be sufficient in Mn, being above the critical limit of 3.0 mg kg^{-1} (Takkar et al. 1989). Manganese deficiency usually does not occur in black soils because a sizeable portion of Mn is bound with manganese oxide which may be readily available (Singh 1988). The adequate Mn content is also reported by Patil and Sonar (1994) and Nasare (2009) in the black soils of Maharashtra.

Based upon the characteristics, these forest soils were classified as typic haplustepts. The all pedons qualified for Inceptisols owing to the presence of cambic horizon and absence of any other diagnostic horizons. Because of ustic moisture regime and a base saturation by sum of cations more 80 per cent in all horizons at a depth between 25 and 75 cm from the mineral soil surface, these two pedons are classified as Typic Haplustepts.

Table 1: Morphological characteristics of soils

Hori-zon	Depth (cm)	Boundary		Matrix colour (Moist)	Texture	Structure			Consistence			Porosity		Roots		Cutans			Effervescence	C.F. (%)	Other features	
		D	T			S	G	Ty	D	M	W	S	Q	S	Q	Ty	Th	Q				
Pedon-1 (Plain land) Anandwan1 (Miyawaki site) : sandy clay, mixed, hyperthermic, Typic Haplustepts																						
Ap	0-20	c	s	10YR 3/4	sc	m	1	cr	sh	fr	ss,ps	f	c	f	c	Fe, mn	tk	c	es	3-8	-	
Bw1	20-53	c	s	10YR 5/4	sc	m	1	cr	sh	fr	ss,ps	f	c	f	c	Fe, mn	tk	c	-	3-8	-	
Bw2	53-98	c	s	10YR 5/4	sc	m	1	abk	sh	fr	ss,ps	f	c	f	c	Fe, mn	tk	c	-	3-8	-	
Bw3	98-150+	C	s	10YR 5/4	sc	m	1	abk	Sh	fr	ss, ps	F	C	F	C	Fe, mn	tk	c	-	-	-	
Pedon-2 (Plain land) Anandwan 2 (VIP plantation site): sandy clay, mixed, hyperthermic, Typic Haplustepts																						
Ap	0-18	c	s	10YR 5/4	sc	m	1	cr	sh	fr	ss,ps	f	c	f	m	Fe, mn	tk	c	es	3-8	-	
Bw1	18-62	c	s	10YR 5/3	sc	m	1	cr	sh	fr	ss,ps	f	m	f	f	Fe, mn	tk	c	-	3-8	-	
Bw2	62-101	c	s	10YR 5/3	sc	m	1	abk	sh	fr	ss,ps	f	c	f	f	Fe, mn	tk	c	-	3-8	-	
BW3	101-150+	c	s	10YR 5/3	sc	m	1	abk	Sh	fr	ss, ps	f	c	f	f	Fe, mn	tk	c	-	3-8	-	

Table2: Chemical and nutrient properties of soil

Hori-zon	Depth (cm)	pH (1:2.5 H ₂ O)	EC (1:2.5 H ₂ O) dSm ⁻¹	Organic Carbon (g/kg)	Available nutrients (kg/ha)			Available micronutrients (mg/kg)					
					N	P	K ⁺	S	Zn	Cu	Fe	Mn	B
Pedon-1 (Plain land) Anandwan1 (miyawaki site) : sandy clay, mixed, hyperthermic, Typic Haplustepts													
Ap	0-20	7.8	0.30	3.3	188	12	453.20	38.08	2.5	0.45	2.62	6.58	0.11
Bw1	20-53	7.1	0.21	2.5	144	08	406.56	15.83	1.8	0.76	2.65	8.78	0.17
Bw2	53-98	6.9	0.18	1.1	64	06	387.76	18.03	3.2	0.53	2.65	2.39	0.14
Bw3	98-150+	6.5	0.13	0.7	43	07	356.12	21.41	2.5	0.45	2.24	2.12	0.25
Pedon-2 (Plain land) Anandwan 2 (VIP plantation site): sandy clay, mixed, hyperthermic, Typic Haplustepts													
Ap	0-18	7.7	0.29	3.4	175	11	462.66	35.22	2.4	0.46	2.72	7.22	0.12
Bw1	18-62	7.2	0.22	2.6	155	09	405.12	22.12	2.1	0.55	2.74	8.12	0.14
Bw2	62-101	6.9	0.21	1.5	72	05	385.12	14.12	1.8	0.44	2.64	2.34	0.21
Bw3	101-150+	6.6	0.11	0.8	47	06	340.22	18.22	2.6	0.57	2.33	3.01	0.19

Pedons descriptions

Pedon: Anandwan

Location	: Anandwan (20°16', 53.5" N and 79°01' 39.0" E)
Elevation	: 216 m above MSL
Landform	: Plain Land
Slope (%)	: 1-3 (0-50 m length)
Erosion	: Slight
Drainage	: Well
Natural vegetation	: Subabul, Neem, Tamrind.
Land Use	: wheat
Parent material	: Basalt (alluvium)
Classification	: Sandy clay,mixed,hyperthermic Typic Haplustepts

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